

Skill-Specific Workforce Scheduling in Service Sector Organizations through Flexible Working Arrangement Clusters

Author Details: Thusitha Rodrigo

Department of Management Science & Engineering Huazhong University of Science & Technology, Wuhan, China

Abstract

This paper focuses on skill-specific workforce scheduling in service sector organizations with variable demands. We use flexible work arrangement (FWA) strategies in obtaining minimal workforce combinations to cater service demand. The problem setting is such that the fluctuating service demand requires continuous availability of skill-specific workforce to provide timely service delivery. The solution combines a skill specific workforce-scheduling model with a selected cluster of FWAs to form an algorithm that (i) minimize labour utilization in a service sector organization with variable demand, (ii) compare the effect of individual and combinations of FWAs in improving the objective function (iii) examine the influence of different FWAs and skill combinations towards increased workforce requirement. We formulate the problem as a mixed integer program with an innovative algorithm to solve it in reasonable computational time. We test the model through a case study on a medium scale South Asian airline MRO (maintenance repair & overhaul) organization with satisfactory results.

Keywords: Operations Research in service organizations, Workforce Scheduling, Flexible work arrangements, Integer programming, airline MRO industry

1. Introduction

Efficient workforce scheduling in the service sector has attracted a considerable amount of research due to its substantial association with operational costs, productivity and the service quality. As a result, main service industries like airlines, hospitals, communications, railways and shipping lines are keen on attaining optimal workforce schedules. An efficient scheduler should be able to allocate a sufficient number of employees to perform different tasks at different timings (i.e., different shifts) which require multiples skills at a minimal cost with optimal productivity.(Ernst, Jiang, Krishnamoorthy, & Sier, 2004; Van Den Bergh, Beliën, De Bruecker, Demeulemeester, & De Boeck, 2013; Ásgeirsson, 2014). When the size of the organization and the number of employees increase with a fluctuating service demand, the problem gets more intricate.(Brucker, Qu, and Burke 2011) Due to highly dynamic decision environment and the diversity of the heterogeneous employee population, personal scheduling problems varies vastly from the other resource allocation problems (Blöchliger 2004). The schedulers have to consider different organizational objectives, regulative constraints, skill levels, optimal costs and fair distribution of workload.

The previous researchers have used numerous approaches to solve personal scheduling problems. Mathematical modeling and heuristics were used extensively due to the complexity and the problem size. Bechtold (1981) distinguish linear programming and construction based heuristics to be the main approaches used in workforce scheduling. However, further review of the literature highlights several methods like integer programming, decomposition, linear programming, metaheuristics, manual solutions, implicit modeling, goal programming, working-set generation and construction/improvement methodologies. (Dijkstra et al. 1991; Lučić and Teodorovic 1999; Mason and Ryan 1998, Deng and Lin 2011; Lavoie, Minoux, and Odier 1988; Teodorovic and Lucic 1998; Iide, Ryan, and Ehr Gott 2010; Vance et al. 1997; Barnhart and Johnson 1995).

This study, focus on workforce scheduling problem of an airline MRO (maintenance repair & overhaul) industry. Aircraft maintenance is a complicated task, which requires a skilled workforce, special equipment, and complicated procedures. Due to this aircraft maintenance is divided into several categories as short term, medium term, and long-term. This classification is based on the time utilization , resources, and execution frequency(Al-Turki 2011). We specifically focus on flight line maintenance (FLM) element, and it is carried out

at the parking terminals of an airport during an aircraft's arrival and departure time gap (i.e., throughout the day) which makes it highly dynamic, time constrained and complex. The FLM workforce is highly skill-specific due to maintenance certifications, competencies, and experiences. On the other hand, every airline is keen on reducing their operational costs to attain a competitive edge in the industries' fierce competition with relatively low-profit margins. Many previous researchers have highlighted that all forms of labor costs are only second to fuel costs in terms of operational expenditures.(PeriyarSelvam et al. 2013; Saltoğlu, Humaira, and Inalhan 2016) In this light, optimal workforce, scheduling is studied as a significant way of minimizing crew costs. Surprisingly, aircraft maintenance workforce scheduling remains as an area of little research compared cabin crew and cockpit crew(Gendreau 2009; Gopalakrishnan and Johnson 2005; Kasirzadeh, Saddoune, and Soumis 2014; Medard and Sawhney 2007). In addition, maintenance workforce scheduling has a direct influence on airline's maintenance routing as well. It is one of the decisive bottlenecks in every airline's planning process and has an obvious impact towards operational expenditures and service reliability. This stresses the need of finding a hybrid solution with managerial insights and mathematical analysis to achieve optimal workforce scheduling.

The research concern on the relationship between organizational outcomes and flexible work arrangements (FAWs) has seen a significant increase in past two decades.(Arvanitis 2005; Eaton 2003; Mayne, Tregaskis, and Brewster 1996; Valverde, Tregaskis, and Brewster 2000) The studies to date have revealed that FWAs have a serious impact on organizations performance. FWAs are studied in both employees and employers perspectives.(Valverde et al. 2000) In order to retain a skilled workforce and to enhance organizational productivity, worldwide service organizations are increasingly resorting to flexibility as an effective tool (Stavrou, Spiliotis, and Charalambous 2010). These organizations are reshaping their job profiles to accommodate more and more flexible work arrangements (FWAs) for their employees. In his early research Kalleberg (2003) highlights job flexibility as crucial essentiality for an organization to survive in the new millennium. The aviation industry is no difference, and mindful adoption of FWAs are highly beneficial, in spite of a marginal number of research executed on this subject. We refer to Berkery et al. (2017) where they segment different clusters of FWAs and their influence on organizational performance by analyzing 1064 different organizations in European Union. More than 42% of those organizations represent service sector, and the authors classify different FAW clusters to suit different types of service organizations.

We further refer to Defraeye and Van Nieuwenhuysse (2016) in their way of scheduling workforce to cater variable service demands. We combine a selected FAW cluster with workforce scheduling to reduce the workforce deployment and to enhance the operational productivity of an airline maintenance organization through skill specific workforce scheduling. In our model, we associate flexibility in maintenance labor capacity by varying number of members in a squad, number of squads in a maintenance group during a specific job duration, flexible shift patterns and flexible work contacts by job sharing (i.e., multi-skilled). Many early literature has focused on individual FWAs where Stavrou (2005) in her research discuss the use of multiple FWA clusters towards organizational performance. Later she collaborated with multiple authors to assess the use of FWA clusters in different types of organizations.(Kassinis and Stavrou 2013; Stavrou, Parry, and Anderson 2015; Stavrou et al. 2010) Apart from these research efforts, the association of multiple FWAs with organizational outcomes remains as an area with little research. As per our knowledge, the use of FWAs as a method for workforce scheduling remains under-explored. Furthermore, many of the existing literature in FWA has focused on the employee perspective rather than an organizational point of view. This leaves a significant gap in existing literature on exploring the effectiveness of FWA clusters in workforce scheduling towards the enhancement of service organizational performance. (Figure 1)

Figure 1

2. Background and Literature review

Over the past few decades, operational researchers have studied the workforce-scheduling problem in different dimensions(Bard and Wan 2008; Brucker et al. 2011; Carrasco 2010; Fowler, Wirojanagud, and Gel 2008; Heimerl and Kolisch 2010; Li, Chen, and Cai 2007; Maik 2010; Pinedo, Zacharias, and Zhu 2015; Tharmmaphornphilas and Norman 2007) . Baker, (1976) classify personal scheduling into *scheduling shifts*, *days off scheduling* and *tour schedule*. Akbari, Zandieh, & Dorri, (2013) argues that scheduling is differentiated by employee's work contracts. They highlight classifications such as full-time, part-time employees and casual workers where the latest addition is the multi-skilled workforce in job-sharing environments (Defraeye and Van Nieuwenhuysse 2016). Many service sector organizations prefer full-time employees. However, the current trend induces some part-time workers as well due to flexible work environments (Hojati and Patil 2011). This has resulted in a mixed workforce with different work contracts. Today is very rare to find organizations either with part-time employees or full-time employees occupying 100% of the workforce. Overstaffing and understaffing are main concerns in contemporary workforce scheduling. Hojati and Patil (2011) solve a problem in a service organization by matching total working hours target with the scheduling horizon with both types of employee contracts. When the regular workforce is insufficient to fulfill coverage constraints, casual and part-time workers are to be deployed. (Brusco 2008; Daniel Wright and Bretthauer 2010; Heimerl and Kolisch 2010).

When service demands are skill specific, heterogeneous groups of employees with diversified skills are required. If the incompetent workforce is detailed for skill-specific tasks, it results in increased operational costs, reduced service quality and lower level of productivity(Simões, Lda, and Gomes 2011).The workforce grouping type is another form of classification. Some scheduling problems are individual employee focused while the others focus on team schedules. Some literature amalgamate variable entities with workforce scheduling problem. The transportation sector is an example where they study amalgamation of employee scheduling with other parallel processes like vehicle routing and maintenance (Hanne, Dornberger, and Frey 2009; Cohn and Barnhart 2003, 2017). In such problems, the routes and number of vehicles are workforces constrained with diversified skills. Airline crew scheduling is a good example of this area of research with numerous literature studying various solution approaches. (Butchers et al. 2001; Gopalakrishnan and Johnson 2005; Kasirzadeh, Saddoune, and Soumis 2014; Klabjan et al. 2001, 2002; Medard and Sawhney 2007; Stojkovi and Soumis 2005; Pamela H.

Vance et al. 1997). In addition, Hanne et al. (2009) discuss crew scheduling in railway industry while Horn, M.E.T., Jiang, H., and Kilby (2006) study patrol boats and crew scheduling problem of the Australian navy .

Some scheduling problems revolve around personal characteristics where they examine *productivity levels* (Akbari et al. 2013; Bagatourova and Mallya 2004), *seniority* (Akbari et al. 2013; Bailyn, Collins, and Song 2007) and *skills* (Helber and Henken 2010). There is a very close relationship between variable productivity levels and skill-based categorization (Thompson and Goodale 2006). The assignment of staff with non-matching skills for demanding tasks results in less profit , extended due dates, inferior service quality and excessive operational costs (Wu and Caves 2000). This adds a penalty on the objective function in skill-based categorization. Both of these characteristics are combined when employees possess heterogeneous skills with variable productivity levels. This is addressed in Bhatnagar, Saddikutti, and Rajgopalan (2007) where they examine learning effects as an additional factor in workforce scheduling. Different grouping decisions such as task assignment, grouping, shift sequencing; service delivery timings, personal preferences, locations, and infrastructure routing are also highlighted in the literature. (Akjiratikarl, Yenradee, and Drake 2007; Azmat, Hürlimann, and Widmer 2004; C. H. Chen, Yan, and Chen 2017; Chu 2007; Di Gaspero et al. 2007; Günther and Nissen 2010; Hanne et al. 2009; Heimerl and Kolisch 2010; Rönnberg and Larsson 2010; Salem M. and Sherali 2007) Horn, M.E.T., Jiang, H. and Kilby (2006) discuss team based scheduling decisions in developing optimal procedures for crew assignment for new fleet of navy boats in Australia. They assign optimal timings for all activities for crewmembers and assign activities for boats or fleets as well. Klabjan et al. (2002), is also based on team-based scheduling where they discuss assigning necessary cockpit and cabin crew to individual aircraft as per the published flight schedules.

Different decision alternatives regarding shift schedules also have been examined. Overlapping and non-overlapping shifts are the main categories. With a distributed demand over the planning horizon (mostly a day) and the time durations are too long to be covered by one shift the basic method is to divide workload into several non-overlapping shifts throughout the day. Most service organizations like hospitals and airlines adopt this method. (Aickelin and Dowsland 2004; Bailyn et al. 2007; Bard and Purnomo 2005; Choi, Hwang, and Park 2009) The common practice is to divide the day into three shifts of 8 hours, and the assignment cost involved with individual shift differs with the timings (i.e., generally the night shifts are more costlier than day shifts). When there is an irregular demand at irregular intervals of the day, this approach is ineffective and needs better ways of scheduling. The overlapping shift concept evolved to cater fluctuating demand of call-centers (Liao et al. 2009). The overlapping shift assignment enables schedulers to assign more staff at peak demand timings and reduce expensive alternative of overtime workers along with the waste of overstaffing at times off peaks. However, the predetermined shift assignment is not efficient even with the overlapping shift patterns, as it does not provide the required flexibility to the employee scheduler.

There are several types of constraints discussed in workforce scheduling literature with main classifications being *hard* and *soft* constraints. The sub-categories are time-related constraints, coverage constraints, sequencing constraints and constraints governing fairness and work balance. When used as *hard*, coverage constraints ensures sufficient workforce at all shifts while minimizing a total number of employees is the objective (Bazargan-Lari, Gupta, and Young 2003; G. Chen et al. 2017; Duffuaa and Al-Sultan 1999). When employees are classified to skill-specific categories, a *hard* constraint is required to ensure availability of sufficient skilled workforce for specific shifts. Some scheduling problems consider skills as *soft* constraints where employees with different skills are treated as an alternative. However, it adds a penalty on the problem outcome and penalizes the objective function. This is commonly discussed in nurse scheduling where Brucker et al. (2010) model different shifts for differently skilled nurses and consider it as a *hard* constraint. Another set of literature focuses on *multi skills* where the workers are trained on skills in addition to their primary skill requirement. This alternative gives the scheduler multiple assignment choices and creates a job sharing

environment. However, this option comes with additional costs in training and higher levels of remuneration for this highly skilled workforce.

Flexible work arrangements (FWAs) differ from traditional office hours and instead refer to patterns of work including weekend work, shift-work, overtime, annual hours contracts, part-time work, job sharing, flexi-time, temporary/casual work, fixed-term contracts, home-based work, teleworking and compressed working weeks.(Kalleberg 2003; Kossek, Barber, and Winters 1999; De Menezes and Kelliher 2011; Stavrou 2005) The concept of FWAs emerged in the 1970s with employers allowing employees with caring responsibilities to come to work later in the mornings, in order to facilitate school drop-offs. This relationship has changed from one of full-time, full-life, full employment (male) and full welfare entitlements (Barbieri 2009) to one with increasing FWAs, more frequent changes between jobs and an increase in the number of female and older workers (Kalleberg 2003). Gareis and Korte (2002) summarize these changes as a shift from a 'regular employment relationship' characterized by full-time permanent jobs, with an even and stable distribution of working hours over a fixed number of days, towards the most recent job paradigm which is characterized by greater flexibility of labor deployment, contributing to greater spatial, contractual and temporary flexibility. This shift has led to a more flexible workforce, allowing labor to be allocated when and where needed.(Jeffrey Hill et al. 2008; Kalleberg 2003; Kassinis and Stavrou 2013; Kossek et al. 1999; De Menezes and Kelliher 2011; Stavrou 2005; Stavrou and Kilaniotis 2010; Valverde et al. 2000)

Although flexibility is inherently an attribute of the workplace, the demand for such flexibility may be on the one hand employee-oriented (Arvanitis 2005), and on the other hand employer-oriented in response to globalization and changing economic circumstances.(Valverde et al. 2000) While the demand for flexibility differs between employees and employers, so too do the various benefits to employees and employers as a result of implementing FWAs. (Jacoby and Matell 1971) Although FWAs can be divided into those that cater for the needs of workers versus those that cater for the needs of the organization, employers ultimately only implement FWAs when the perceived benefits outweigh the costs of introducing such practices. (Defraeye and Van Nieuwenhuysse 2016; Jacoby and Matell 1971; Mayne et al. 1996; Munsch, Ridgeway, and Williams 2014; Stavrou et al. 2015; Valverde et al. 2000)

Airline crew scheduling has undergone extensive research during past few decades in search of optimal solutions (a. T. Ernst et al. 2004). Due to cost constraints involved, even a minor percentile saving leads to considerable cost reductions annually (Sasaki and Nishi 2016).According to Gopalakrishnan & Johnson (2005) , airline staffing and scheduling problem cover a large span of complexities ranging from aircraft routing, assignment, scheduling, crew rostering, scheduling and assignment. Lavoie et al. (1988) formulate a large-scale set covering problem with many columns where each represents a valid crew pairing. Ryan (1992) introduces a generalized set partitioning model for aircrew scheduling involving more than 650 constraints and 200,000 binary variables. Yan & Chang (2002) discuss cockpit crew scheduling in specific as the salary and remuneration of the pilots cover a significant portion of the overall crew costs. They formulate a set partitioning model and solve it through column generation. Deng & Lin (2011) use an ant-colony optimization based algorithm to solve airline crew scheduling problem with numerous enumerations. Mercier & Soumis (2007) solve the optimal crew-scheduling problem along with aircraft routing and retiming. These three areas are interdependent on each other and linking these constraints together ensures the same schedule is used for both aircraft routing and crew scheduling. Kasirzadeh, Saddoune, & Soumis (2014) presents a detailed review on crew scheduling models and methods discussed since the year 2014. As highlighted above, a majority of the of the crew scheduling research are allied with complex mathematics and heuristics mainly due to the complex nature (Barnhart and Cohn 2004).

As per Medard and Sawhney (2007), a majority of the airline crew scheduling problems focus on flying crew and the emphasis applied to ground maintenance crew scheduling is relatively less. The problem setting of the

two types is also diverse in nature due to several reasons. Unlike flying crew (inclusive of cockpit and cabin crew), the ground maintenance crew is stationed at the airline's base airport and do not move from one location to another. Further, the requirement of maintenance certification distinguishes the maintenance crew from the flying element. Hence, the general crew scheduling techniques need adjustments before being applied to ground maintenance crew.

Flight line maintenance (FLM) crew scheduling is an integral part of the overall aircraft maintenance where optimal resource utilization, cost reduction, and safety are prime concerns. Gupta et al. (2003) define line maintenance as a set of regular inspections, lubrication and physical checks conducted during an aircraft's arrival and departure time slot. It is conducted at the passenger boarding gates in coherence with the departure timetable (Simões et al. 2011). On time completion of flight-line maintenance affects overall timetables and a delay would adversely affect flight departures. FLM scheduling is a tough task as it involves many variables like timetables, personal commitments, labor regulations, and infrastructure capacity limitations. It gets further complicated with unexpected scenarios like delayed flight arrivals as it creates a fluctuating demand. The requirement of maintenance certification further exaggerates the planning complexity. An approved maintenance type certification is essential for every crewmember who work on commercial jetliners. This is a strict regulation throughout the industry with zero tolerance. The maintenance manpower demand fluctuates throughout the day with significant peaks and off-peak. This makes capacity planning more challenging. Hence, formulation of an optimal crew capacity plan with maximum work output and minimal cost is a challenging task.

3. Problem setting and mathematical modeling

In this section, we formulate a general model for several service sector workforce-scheduling problems such as aviation, healthcare, transportation, and hospitality industry. We use mixed linear integer programming (MILP) technique to form the mathematical model and discuss the solution criteria through an innovative algorithm that significantly reduces the problem size and the computational time. In the service sector, demand is dependent on the type of service required. Employees are directly involved with several elements to cater that demand. Our model defines these demand creating elements as either machines or items. For example, it may refer to patients in the healthcare sector, vehicles in transport sector and aircraft in the aviation sector. All these services require teams of employees who are grouped into different squads with several functional classifications (i.e., skill specific, gender specific, age specific and etc.) wherein this model consider only the skill classification. The planning horizons vary from a day to several weeks depending on the demand profile. The model enables the scheduler to plan for variable planning horizons with different shift sequences. However, the number of shifts operate in a specific time-slot of a specific date needs to be defined carefully as it is one of the main decision variables of the model. We show an example of defining this in chapter four in our case study.

In addition, to reflect the reality and to facilitate a feasible solution several assumptions and limitations are highlighted in advance. The model assumes that service demand for each machine/item is known for each timeslot. For the same type of machine/item, the shift starting time is same every day during the entire planning horizon. If the shift starting time of a specific service team is to be varied every day, it imposes an unnecessary inconvenience on employees. In order to derive a practical solution, there should be feasible ranges assigned for the number of shifts in a day, number of employees in a squad and number of squads in a team. The model has its limitations as well. First, it requires an accurate service demand forecast as its input. Second, this model can only accommodate planned service demand only where the uncertainties like delays, unplanned events, and employee shortages are not incorporated. Third, it assumes the service department has a sufficient number of employees to accommodate computational results.

3.1 Problem formulation

Nomenclature

<u>Set</u>	<u>Description</u>
A	Set of different machines/items
a	(a th) Type of machine/item, where (a ∈ A)
J	Set of days included in planning horizon (i.e. schedule) , J ≡ {0,1,2 α}
j	(j th) Day of schedule, where (j ∈ J)
W	Set of different work contracts
w	(w th) Type of work contract, where (w ∈ W)
G	Set of all service teams
g	(g th) Service team, where (g ∈ G)
C	Set of different squads
c	(c th) Type squad, where (c ∈ C)
S	Set of shift starting times in a day with one-hour time slots, where S ≡ {0, 1, 2.....β}
s	(s th)Shift starting time, where (s ∈ S)
v	(v th) Time slot, where (v ∈ S)

Parameters Description

m _c	Number of employees in (c) type squad
t _w	Duration of (w) type of work contract
θ	Lower bound of the number of shifts in a day
ρ	Upper bound of the number of shifts in a day
f	Lower bound of the number of type (c) job squads
h	Upper bound of the number of type (c) job squads
γ	Lower bound of the number of technicians in (c) type job squad
δ	Upper bound of the number of technicians in (c) type job squad
X	A very large positive value
Z	Objective function

Variable Description

D _{ja} ^v	Service demand for (a th) type of machine on (j th) day at (v th) time slot (i.e., manpower demand in terms of <i>number of employees</i>)
L _{jsga} ^v	Minimum service demand fulfilled by (g th) team on (j th) day (v th) time slot at (s th)Shift starting time (i.e. manpower demand in terms of <i>man-hours</i>)
y _s	Availability of a shift (s) during a specific time slot S ≡ {0, 1, 2.....β}, where (y _s) is a binary variable;
N _{jv}	Set of all shifts which operate at (v th) time slot of (j th) day in the week
U _{jwgc} ^s	Number of (c) type squads in (g) team with (w) type of work contracts on (j th) day at (s) shift starting time

(W^m) Model

$$\text{Min } Z = \sum_{j \in J} \sum_{s \in S} \sum_{g \in G} \sum_{c \in C} \sum_{w \in W} m_c t_w U_{jwgc}^s \quad (1)$$

$$\text{s.t. } y_s = 0 \text{ or } 1 \quad \forall s \in S \quad (2)$$

$$\theta \leq \sum_{s \in S} y_s \leq \rho \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{j \in J} \sum_{g \in G} \sum_{c \in C} \sum_{w \in W} U_{jwgc}^s \leq (X)y_s \quad \forall s \in S \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{(j,s) \in N_{jv}} \sum_{g \in G} L_{jsga}^v \geq D_{ja}^v \quad \forall j \in J, s \in S, a \in A \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{c \in C} \sum_{w \in W} m_c U_{jwgc}^s \geq \sum_{a \in A} L_{jsga}^v \quad \forall j \in J, s \in S, g \in G, v \in \{v | (j, s) \in N_{jv}\} \quad (6)$$

$$f \leq U_{jwgc}^s \leq h \quad f, h \geq 0 \text{ and } h > f \quad (7)$$

$$\gamma \leq m_c \leq \delta \quad \gamma, \delta \geq 0 \text{ and } \delta > \gamma \quad (8)$$

$$U_{jwgc}^s \geq 0 \quad U_{jwgc}^s \in I \quad (9)$$

$$L_{jsga}^v \geq 0 \quad \forall j \in J, c \in C, s \in S, g \in G, v \in \{v | (j, s) \in N_{jv}\} \quad (10)$$

The objective function (Z) in equation (1), minimize total man-hours requirement by minimizing; the number of employees in (c) type squad, duration of (w) type of work contracts and number of (c) type squads in (g) team with (w) type of work contracts on (jth) day at (s) shift is starting time. Equation (3) limits the total number of shifts in a day to a feasible range. Equation (4) denotes that service team is assigned for work only when a shift exists. Equation (5) denotes that employees assigned for work must be able to fulfil the service demand of all machines during each time slot within their respective shifts. Equation (6) denotes that all employees, for every machine type should fulfil the minimum service demand of all machines in each time slot. Equation (7) gives the flexibility to the scheduler to define a feasible range of squads in a group. Equation (8) define the minimum to maximum number of employees in a squad. Equations (2, 9, and 10) are integer and non-negativity constraints.

An important aspect of the model is its ability to match the skill-specific employees with the service demand. A squad is the basic workforce element, and in a team comprised of several squads. As mentioned above some tasks which require an identical set of skills are performed in the same time slot. Accordingly, the squads in same service team must have the same set of skills. In other words, the service teams correspond to the same set of skills required by the tasks available at the specific time slot. In addition, scheduling and employees assignment for each shift is done at the squad level. The service demand for every one-hour time slot, (D_{ja}^v) is estimated employee wise (i.e., the number of employees required). However, (U_{jwgc}^s) denotes a squad with several employees and their work contract may vary duration wise. (i.e., normal employees with full shifts or job sharing with half shifts) Therefore, in order to match the service demand with employee capacity, we need to aggregate all variables represented by (U_{jwgc}^s) (i.e., flexi-shift, flexi-time, flexi-grouping and job sharing). As the two variables (D_{ja}^v) and (U_{jwgc}^s) are measured differently, (i.e., number of employees vs number of man-hours) we had to define an intermediate variable (L_{jsga}^v) to facilitate the relationship. It represents minimum service demand fulfilled by a team on a specific time slot in terms of man-hours and bridge the gap between input (D_{ja}^v) and output (U_{jwgc}^s).

3.2 Model expansion with a selected FWA cluster

As per Berkery et al. (2017), a selected cluster of FAWs (i.e., flexi-shift, flexi-time, flexi-grouping and job sharing) are used to improve the scheduling model (W^m). Subsequently, another seven sub-models are derived from (W^m) with different combinations of FAWs. If we consider a model with no flexible work arrangements and denote it by (W) then the following sub-models are improvements of (W).

<u>Flexi-models</u>	<u>Description</u>
W_S	Flexi-shifts
W_G	(Flexi-employees in squads + Flexi-squads in teams) = Flexi-grouping
W_W	(Flexi- time + Job sharing + work contracts) = Flexi-work hours
W_{SG}	Flexi-shifts + Flexi-grouping
W_{SW}	Flexi-shifts + Flexi-work hours
W_{GW}	Flexi-grouping + Flexi-work hours
W_{SGW}	Flexi-shifts + Flexi-grouping + Flexi-work hours

Further, it is to be realized that W^m is same as W_{SGW} where (U_{jwcg}^s) vary all FAWs. In addition, the most complicated model in terms of computational effort is (W_{SGW}) and one can never conclude that the most feasible solution is derived through it. Therefore, other six sub-models also need to be solved to compare the results.

3.3 Solution algorithm

The FAW workforce scheduling model ($W_{SGW} = W^m$) solution process is complex and requires a heavy computational effort. Different variables like machine/item types, number of employees in a team, different skill combinations, variable shifts and their starting times along with the model constraints add to the complexity and the problem size. Therefore, we develop an algorithm to solve this efficiently and then to solve the sub-problems become much easier. The initial idea is to find out the lower boundary of the solution space, which gives a starting point. In order to narrow down the search region towards a feasible solution, we use tabu search. We simplify (W^m) by generating two subproblems, which reduce variables and constraints. This in return will reduce the problem size.

We simplify several variables in the first sub-problem, solve them and fix the values obtained. Then those values are used as inputs to the second sub-problem to achieve a feasible solution. We assume that all machines/items are identical and therefore all employees could fulfill the service demand with no skill variation. In other words, this will ease out the skill classification and different teaming constraints. As a result, variables (A, a, G, g) are relaxed from the problem. The two variables (D_{ja}^v), (U_{jwcg}^s) are redefined neglecting machine differences, teaming constraint and thereby skill classification is automatically relaxed. Then the intermediate (L_{jsga}^v) variable is automatically removed as both the input and output are calculated in terms of man-hours. The formulation of the first sub-problem denoted by (W_{sub1}^m) is as below;

<u>Variables</u>	<u>Description</u>
D_j^v	Service demand on (j^{th}) day at (v^{th}) time slot
U_{jwc}^s	Number of (c) type squads with (w) type of work contracts on (j^{th}) day at (s) shift starting time

(W_{sub1}^m) Sub-Model

$$\text{Min } Z = \sum_{j \in J} \sum_{s \in S} \sum_{c \in C} \sum_{w \in W} m_c t_w U_{jwc}^s \quad (11)$$

$$\text{s.t. } y_s = 0 \text{ or } 1 \quad \forall s \in S \quad (12)$$

$$\theta \leq \sum_{s \in S} y_s \leq \rho \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{(j,s) \in N_{jv}} \sum_{c \in C} \sum_{w \in W} U_{jwc}^s \geq D_j^v \quad \forall s \in S \quad (14)$$

$$f \leq U_{jwc}^s \leq h \quad f, h \geq 0 \text{ and } h > f \quad (15)$$

$$\gamma \leq m_c \leq \delta \quad \gamma, \delta \geq 0 \text{ and } \delta > \gamma \quad (16)$$

$$U_{jwc}^s \geq 0 \quad U_{jwc}^s \in I \quad (17)$$

Model (W_{sub1}^m) implies that each employee can fulfil the demand of every machine/item and thereby simplify the problem size significantly through relaxing variables associated with machine types, teaming and skills. So theoretically, the solution of (W_{sub1}^m) is the *lower boundary* of the optimal solution of (W^m). However, this solution does not explicitly address the skill combinations except for the fact that all employees are skilled to work with all machines/items and thereby does not guarantee a feasible solution. Therefore, our next step is to solve the problem for all possible skill combinations using the feasible shifts and their starting times achieved through (W_{sub1}^m). We formulate the second sub-problem denoted by (W_{sub2}^m) as below;

Parameter Description

K Set of shift starting times in a day generated by (W_{sub1}^m)

K_{jv} Set of all feasible shifts generated by (W_{sub1}^m)

(W_{sub2}^m) Sub-Model

$$\text{Min } Z = \sum_{j \in J} \sum_{s \in K} \sum_{g \in G} \sum_{c \in C} \sum_{w \in W} m_c t_w U_{jwcg}^s \quad (18)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \sum_{(j,s) \in K_{jv}} \sum_{g \in G} L_{jsga}^v \geq D_{jA}^v \quad \forall j \in J, s \in S, a \in A \quad (19)$$

$$\sum_{c \in C} \sum_{w \in W} m_c U_{jwcg}^s \geq \sum_{a \in A} L_{jsga}^v \quad \forall j \in J, s \in S, g \in G, v \in \{v | (j, s) \in K_{jv}\} \quad (20)$$

$$f \leq U_{jwcg}^s \leq h \quad f, h \geq 0 \text{ and } h > f \quad (21)$$

$$\gamma \leq m_c \leq \delta \quad \gamma, \delta \geq 0 \text{ and } \delta > \gamma \quad (22)$$

$$U_{jwcg}^s \geq 0 \quad U_{jwcg}^s \in I \quad (23)$$

$$L_{jsga}^v \geq 0 \quad \forall j \in J, c \in C, s \in S, g \in G, v \in \{v | (j, s) \in K_{jv}\} \quad (24)$$

Even though the problem size of model (W_{sub2}^m) get simplified by fixing shifts and their starting types, the (*service teams*) variable still takes a large value due to different types of machine/items and different skill combinations. We use a tabu search that can enumerate all possible skill combinations. It is obvious that all organizations favor employees with multiple skills. For example, if one employee is having only a single skill pertaining to machines/items, he/she has to idle during other shifts, which involves different machines/items. On the other hand, it is not practical for all employees to be multi-skilled and to serve all machine/item demands. Therefore the feasible solution is to be arrived by limiting the number of skill requirement and continuing with deriving feasible solutions. This is further illustrated in the case study.

4. Case study

4.1 Model enhancement towards a case study

We now develop our model to accommodate flight line maintenance manpower demand by scheduling an optimal number of employees to a flexible shift pattern. This covers the stage III of the overall workforce capacity planning of airline maintenance as indicated in figure 2. Different aircraft have variable maintenance demands, and the airlines have a rotating demand cycle with significant peaks and off-peak (Figure 3). Flexible work arrangements are a good option in catering such stochastic service demand (Duffuaa and Al-Sultan 1999; Morton and Popova 2004; Rosenberger et al. 2000; Yen and Birge 2006; Zhu and Sherali 2009).

Figure 2

In our model, employee teams are formed with a flexible number of job squads and a flexible number of employees in a squad. We form multi-skilled jobs squads with different maintenance certificate (i.e., skills) combinations. The grouping of the teams corresponds to the varying maintenance demand formed by different aircraft combinations. This eases the maintenance certification complexity and enables job squads to work on several aircraft types using multiple certifications. The number of employees in a job squad vary from two to four. The squad’s maintenance certification composition depends on the maintenance demand of the shift starting time. The main advantages of this strategy are the scheduling flexibility and the less amount of overtime.

In addition, we use a flexible shift pattern with shift starting time throughout the day at one-hour intervals. We also use job sharing strategy through cross-trained employees for flight line maintenance duties. This has two distinct advantages over hiring part-time workers and costly overtime schedules. Aircraft maintenance require a highly specialized technical workforce with maintenance type certifications issued through their organizations; which makes it impossible to hire part-time workers from outside organizations. Additionally, if overtime is used as means of satisfying excessive demand; it incurs high labor costs. According to the model, the full-time employees work a single job duration (i.e., at least 8 hours) continuously while the job-sharing employees are used only for a half job duration. As mentioned above (N_{jv}), (i.e., the set of all shifts, which operate at (v^{the}) time slot of (j^{the}) day in the week) is a case-specific variable, and we define it as below;

a. For normal employees who work 8-hour shifts

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{If } v \in \{0,1, \dots, 6\}, N_{jv} &= \{(j', s') | j' = (j + 6) \bmod 7, 17 + v \leq s' \leq 23\} \quad (25) \\
 N_{jv} &= \cup \{(i', v') | j' = j, 0 \leq s' \leq v\} \quad \forall j \\
 &\text{Otherwise, } N_{jv} = \{(j, s') | i - 7 \leq s' \leq i\}
 \end{aligned}$$

b. For job-sharing employees who work 4-hour shifts

$$N_{jv} = \begin{cases} \text{If } v \in \{0,1, \dots,6\}, N_{jv} = \{(j', s') | j' = (j + 6) \bmod 7, 21 + v \leq s' \leq 23\} \\ \cup \{(i', v') | j' = j, 0 \leq s' \leq v\} & \forall j \\ \text{Otherwise, } N_{jv} = \{(j, s') | i - 3 \leq s' \leq i\} \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

Figure 3 (Average maintenance demand)

4.2 Model implementation

We used the maintenance organization of a medium scale Asian airline as our case study. The airline operates towards 94 international destinations, a member of “One-world” alliance since 2014 and has code-sharing alliances with 17 other international airlines. Out of several types maintenance schedules, we considered the flight line maintenance department as it is the most dynamic and complicated. Majority of the maintenance department’s customer base comprised of six midsize jetliners; Airbus A318, Airbus A320, A320neo, A321, Airbus A330 and Boing 737. The planning horizon was one week and for this study, the average hourly maintenance man-hours demand was aggregated over a period of 10 planning weeks (Figure 3). As per the existing maintenance practice, flight line maintenance operates on a shift basis with four employees in a squad. A day was divided into three eight hour shifts with shift starting times 0000hrs, 0800hrs, and 1600hrs. The MILP model was tested with 3 to 6 shift range, 4 to 8-hour work contracts, and the squad sizes varied from 2 to 4. The shift starting time could be any hour of the day. The integer model was solved using IBM ILOG CPLEX Optimizer studio programming software on an ASUS i7 personnel computer. To reduce computational burden, solution satisfactoriness was set to 5% gap (error margin) from the lower bound obtained by the intermediate model (W_{sub1}^m) and the computational threshold time was set to maximum 500 seconds. Except for few iterations, the majority of the problems were solved within the set boundaries. In the analysis, the mathematical model’s results were compared against the heuristics computed with the existing maintenance practice.

First, we examined the flexi-shifts, FAW strategy. For the solution to be practical, we varied the number of shifts from 3 to 6 where the shift starting times spanned throughout the day with one-hour intervals. As per the results, (figure 4) the best shift combination was found to be six shift starting times (i.e., 1 pm, 7 pm, 8 pm, 9 pm, 10 pm and 5 pm). This is mainly due to a large number of shifts corresponds to an increased number of solutions. It is to be noted that the man-hours reduction between three shifts combination and four is the most significant and afterward there is a small development. Hence we recommend the decision makers to analyze the trade-off between advantage gained through an increased number of shifts in a day and the scheduling

complexity faced by an enhanced number of shifts. However, the model provides the insights that the existing pattern is far below from the optimal solution. In addition, the average maintenance demand in Figure x roughly matched with the best shift starting times (Figure 5) as well indicating the feasibility of the model.

Figure 4 (Number of shifts corresponding to man-hours requirement)

Figure 5 (Distribution of best shifts sequence)

A comparative analysis (Figure 6) of the seven flexi-models using a value defined as “Percentage increment.” (P_{in}) against heuristics computed as per existing maintenance practice. If the heuristic (H) results are the values for (P_{in}) with regard (W_{sub2}^m) to was calculated as below;

$$(P_{in}) = \left\{ \frac{[(H) - (W_{sub2}^m)]}{(H)} \right\} \times 100 \tag{27}$$

The same equation substituting (W_{sub1}^m) is used to calculate values for (W_{sub1}^m) as well. The individual (P_{in}) values of the flexi-models against the heuristics are plotted. In order to ease the comparison with the available practice, the number of shifts considered for integer model was fixed to three and flexible corresponding starting times were selected. The flexi-models pertaining to both sub-models are compared. The different work contracts were generalized by converting half-time employees contracts (i.e., job sharing) into an equivalent number of normal contracts.

Figure 6 (A comparison of individual flexi models output with heuristics)

The results indicate the model with all FWAs is the best solution. It has an overall increment of 24.18% over the heuristics as it requires the least amount of workforce. Therefore the use of FAWs are definitely saved valuable man-hours for the airline, and the selected FWA cluster can be easily applied in practical terms for many service sector organizations. When the output of the single flexi-models are considered, flexi-shifts gives the highest improvement at 6.55%, then flexi-working hours at 5.26% and least being flexi-grouping 3.04%. All these results were calculated for (W_{sub2}^m) as it only resembles the practical scenario with different aircraft types and different sill combinations. As the impact of flexi-shifts was discussed earlier, we then examined the impact of flexi-working hours. In addition, the results indicate that all combinations of other flexi-strategies with flexi-working has better solutions than (W_W). The best combination except for optimal (W_{SGW}) is flexi-working hours with flexi grouping (W_{GW}) with an overall improvement of 20.84%. This indicates that the airline could attain relatively satisfactory results even with a fixed number of shifts and shift starting times. The fixed shifts sequence obviously makes the scheduling far easier than the flexi-shift scheduling. However, it is an organization specific decision where the decision makers should evaluate the trade-off between advantages and disadvantages. Out of the three dual combinations (i.e. W_{SG} , W_{SW} , W_{GW}), shift and work hour combination (W_{SW}) is the least effective with only 7.9% improvement. When comparing with the flexi-shift individual improvement of 6.55%, this is only a minor advance. In addition, there is an added cost concern with job sharing strategy, as it requires multi-skilled employees who definitely demand higher remunerations than the rest. This again needs the decision makers concern with an analysis of the advantages and disadvantages.

Figure 7 (Influence of Skills towards differentiating output of the two models)

The gap between (W_{sub1}^m) and (W_{sub2}^m) graphs in figure x represent the influence of skill-specific scheduling towards increasing the maintenance man-hours requirement. In other words, if all aircraft types are the same and if all employees could work on each aircraft, the two graphs become identical and overlap on each other. Therefore in figure x, we compared the percentage difference of individual flexi-models to evaluate their sensitivity to skill combinations. The results reveal several interesting findings where flex-grouping and working-hours combination (W_{GW}) is highly sensitive to skill combinations at 5.76% and is even higher than (W_{SGW}) at 3.93% which is the most complicated combination. In addition, (W_S) is the highest sensitivity model in terms of individual strategies at 4.51%, where it becomes the lowest when combined with flexible-working hours at 2.79%. However, the optimal solution (W_{SGW}) at 3.93% is in a mediocre sensitivity level and therefore once again conforms the feasibility of the model. The percentage difference of (W_{sub2}^m) relative to (W_{sub1}^m) was calculated as below;

$$\text{Percentage difference} = \left\{ \frac{[(W_{sub1}^m) - (W_{sub2}^m)]}{(W_{sub1}^m)} \right\} \times 100 \quad (28)$$

5. Conclusion

In this paper, we focused on workforce scheduling problem of service sector organizations with variable demands, through a study of an airline's maintenance workforce. The main differences between the operating environment compared to normal scheduling scenarios is the requirement of the multi-skilled workforce with different skill combinations to cater variable service demand throughout the day. Managing workforce with different skill combinations in complicated demand environment with traditional work arrangements is a challenging task. A solution to this enigma was derived from a contemporary trend in human resource management; Flexible work arrangements. This gave us the possibility to design employee work hours around variable service demand rather than around the traditional shift structures.

Through an integer-programming model, we solved the workforce-scheduling problem that arises in this context with flexible work arrangements. The objective of the model was to minimize the workforce supply while satisfying the service demand of each time slot. We defined service demand as the culmination of the services demanded by machines/items that was time bound with fixed intervals. This service demand required known but variable skill combinations due to differences in machines/items. A team formation strategy is adapted to assign employees to these tasks. However such problem environments demand various skill combinations, shift schedule combinations and grouping combinations which makes the proposed integer program both complex and huge in practical implication. Therefore, we develop a more feasible solution algorithm by decomposing the original problem into hierarchical sub-problems. The first sub-problem assume uniform machines/items to find best possible shift schedule. Then we solve the second sub-problem for best skill combination for multiple machines/items by taking fixed shift schedule as an input from the first case. The algorithm solves the two subproblems subsequently to obtain a feasible solution.

The effectiveness of the proposed model and the algorithm is tested using an airline case study. The reason for selecting aviation maintenance workforce scheduling to test our model is the fact its complexity in operation as a service industry example. The primary results indicate satisfactory output in terms of minimizing skill specific workforce. Therefore, we believe the model is compatible with other service environments as well with industry-specific modifications.

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